

SENSOR ARRAY PROCESSOR EVALUATION WITH A STANDARDIZED TEST CASE (STC)

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Abstract

A standard test case (STC) [15] for the comparative evaluation of the plethora of modern space-time signal processing (STSP) techniques is summarized. The STC is thought to be realistic in the context of superimposed multiple discrete and continuous ambient noise fields for a uniform linear array (ULA) of sensors. Attention is given the MUSIC direction finder (DF), the ESPRIT DF, the linear prediction (LP) based DF and the Enhanced Minimum Variance Distortionless Response (EMVDR) beamformer (BF). The asymptotic estimate of the source subspace dimensionality is used and the performance of several algorithms for the estimation of the dominant source subspace spanning eigenvectors are evaluated with respect to convergence rate and variance. The issue of false alarms induced by overestimating the source subspace dimensionality relative to the actual number of discrete sources is discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

A requirement in many modern STSP systems is the simultaneous detection and location of multiple angularly extended and/or threshold sources and not simply the angular resolution of two equal strength high SNR sources. Foremost among the modern STSP techniques are those which are based first, on the estimation of the dimensionality of the source subspace and, secondly, on the estimation of an orthonormal (eigenvector) basis for either all or part of the source subspace. Given a mixture of very low SNR and angularly extended sources which are parametrically undefined both dimensionality and basis estimation are formidable problems. The extraction of a "dominant" source subspace which contains sources near a low false alarm detection threshold is extremely difficult.

First, several algorithms for estimating a limited number of eigenvectors are examined. This is motivated by a subsequent consideration of beamforming (BF) techniques which do not require an estimate of the complete source subspace dimensionality and direction finding techniques which do require such an estimate. The EMVDR BF requires only an estimate of a minimal number of source subspace dominant eigenvectors. The

DF techniques considered are provided with the information theoretic asymptotic, i.e. correct estimate of the source subspace dimensionality. The BF and DF candidates considered are compared on the basis of temporal detection events as a function of possible source arrival angle. No attempt is made to prewhiten the data because the number and characteristics of the extended sources is assumed to be unknown. Moreover, no attempt is made to resolve correct source detections from false alarms because such techniques have not been proven reliable for sources at the detection threshold.

2. SUBSPACE ESTIMATORS

Dominant subspace techniques such as EMVDR [10], MUSIC [12] and ESPRIT [11] are currently popular as high-resolution methods for direction-of-arrival (DOA) estimation of plane waves by an array of sensors. The computational complexity of the eigendecomposition of the cross spectral density matrix, however, has prohibited real-time implementation.

This section of the paper investigates new classes of dominant subspace algorithms which help alleviate the computational burden. These estimators reduce complexity from $O(N^3)$ to $O(ND^2)$, where D is the dimension of the dominant subspace.

Yang and Kaveh [1] have proposed an adaptive estimator of the complete source or noise subspace based on a gradient search method. Schreiber [2] presented a method which exploits repeated eigenvalues by deflating the source subspace before updating its spectral decomposition. Owsley [3] introduced an adaptive procedure to estimate the source subspace based on orthogonal iteration. Tufts and Melissinos [5] have developed a Prony-Lanczos method to approximate the source subspace. Karasalo [6] developed a method which averages a deflated source subspace.

For notational simplicity, assume that we are estimating source subspaces only, and that their dimension is D .

3. PERFORMANCE METRICS

Four performance metrics were chosen to examine the convergence and accuracy of the proposed estimators. The first metric termed "eigenvector inner product" α is used primarily to examine convergence.

Let $\mathbf{x}(p)$ be the signal vector received from an N sensor ULA at time index p . Let $p = 1, 2, \dots, P$, the total number of snapshots. Define $\mathbf{R} = E\{\mathbf{x}(p)\mathbf{x}(p)^H\}$, the cross spectral density matrix (CSDM), where $E\{\cdot\}$ denotes the expectation of $\{\cdot\}$. Define the spectral decomposition of \mathbf{R} :

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{M}^H$$

where $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_N)$ is a diagonal matrix of eigenvalues ordered so that $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_N$, "H" denotes the Hermitian transpose, and $\mathbf{M} = [\mathbf{m}_1, \mathbf{m}_2, \dots, \mathbf{m}_N]$ where \mathbf{m}_i is the i -th normalized eigenvector of \mathbf{R} associated with λ_i . Let $\hat{\mathbf{R}}(p)$ be the estimated CSDM at time index p , obtained recursively from a rank-one update

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}(p) = \mu\hat{\mathbf{R}}(p-1) + (1-\mu)\mathbf{x}(p)\mathbf{x}(p)^H$$

where $0 \leq \mu \leq 1$. The initial value for $\hat{\mathbf{R}}(p)$

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}(-1) = \epsilon\mathbf{I}_N + \frac{1}{P} \sum_{p=1}^P \mathbf{x}(p)\mathbf{x}(p)^H$$

where $\epsilon \ll 1$, \mathbf{I}_N is the identity matrix, $P \ll P$ and the summation is the block estimate of the P -th order CSDM. Let $\hat{\mathbf{M}}(p)$ be a matrix of normalized eigenvectors $\hat{\mathbf{M}}(p) = [\hat{\mathbf{m}}(p)_1, \hat{\mathbf{m}}(p)_2, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{m}}(p)_N]$ where $\hat{\mathbf{m}}(p)_i$ is the i -th normalized eigenvector of $\hat{\mathbf{R}}(p)$, obtained from a *dominant subspace estimation algorithm*. The initial value for $\hat{\mathbf{M}}(p)$, $\hat{\mathbf{M}}(-1) \leftarrow \text{SVD}(\hat{\mathbf{R}}(-1))$, was obtained from the MATLAB [8] algorithm.

The inner product

$$\alpha(p)_i = |\hat{\mathbf{m}}(p)_i^H \mathbf{m}_i|, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, D$$

where $0 \leq \alpha_i \leq 1$ and $D < N$ is the order of the dominant subspace is used as the *first* metric of convergence.

The second metric β tracks the accuracy of the first D eigenvalues produced by an estimator.

Define the diagonal matrix

$$\Delta(p) = \hat{\mathbf{M}}(p)^H \hat{\mathbf{R}}(p) \hat{\mathbf{M}}(p) = \text{diag}(\hat{\lambda}(p)_1, \hat{\lambda}(p)_2, \dots, \hat{\lambda}(p)_D)$$

where $\hat{\lambda}(p)_i$ represents the i -th eigenvalue of $\hat{\mathbf{R}}(p)$. The diagonal elements of $\Delta(p)$

$$\beta(p)_i = \hat{\lambda}(p)_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, D$$

were used as the second convergence metric. Graphs associated with this metric are not shown.

The third metric $e_{\alpha, \beta}$ termed "convergence RMS error" compares α and β with their true or steady-state value. Using this metric, it is possible to quantize the performance of an estimator using a single number. Define τ as the number of samples allowed for transient settling. For snapshots $\mathbf{x}(p)$, $p = \tau+1, \tau+2, \dots, P$, define two RMS error calculations

$$e(p)_\alpha = [\text{mean}((1 - \alpha(p)_i)^2)]^{1/2}$$

$$e(p)_\beta = [\text{mean}((\beta(p)_i - \lambda_i)^2)]^{1/2}$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, D$.

The fourth metric is a bearing-time display which portrays peak information from various spectrum estimators. A block diagram of the technique used is helpful:

Figure 1 - Bearing-time Display

The spectrum estimators considered are

- 1) Conventional Beamforming (CBF).
- 2) MVDR BF [13].
- 3) LP DF [9].
 - order of predictor = 23.
- 4) EMVDR BF [10].
 - unit enhancement, number of modes $D = 1, 3, 5$.
 - enhancement $e = 10^8$, $D = 3$.
- 5) MUSIC DF [12].
 - number of modes $D = 13$.
- 6) ESPRIT DF [11].
 - number of modes $D = 13$.

The peak-picker operates on a three-point rule to calculate local minima. Given three adjacent points A , B and C on a bearing response a peak B is detected if $B > A$ and $B > C$. The three point rule is slid along the bearing response curve. Finally, bearing response for the infinitely averaged CSDM is an overlay for the bearing-time display. Since ESPRIT is purely a direction-finding algorithm, the overlay for ESPRIT DOA angles are straight dotted lines.

4. RESULTS

Results for estimator comparison were obtained from the following parameters $P = 1000$ snapshots, $P = 3$ snapshots, $\tau = 200$ snapshots, $\mu = 0.99$ and the dimension of the dominant subspace $D = 3$.

The graphs in Figure 2 show the performance of the inner product α metric versus time for the six subspace estimators.

Figure 2a - gradient search [1]

Figure 2b - subspace iteration [2]

Figure 2c - orthogonal iteration [3,4]

Figure 2d - LINPACK ZSVDC [14]

Figure 2e - Prony-Lanczos [5]

Figure 2f - signal subspace averaging [6]

The following table summarizes performance in terms of RMS error.

TYPE	e_{α_i} (dB)			e_{β_i} (dB)		
	$i=1$	$i=2$	$i=3$	$i=1$	$i=2$	$i=3$
Gradient Search	-7.078	-7.709	-5.661	3.346	1.058	-1.934
Subspace Iteration	-6.378	-4.398	-2.195	5.794	8.072	3.517
Orthogonal Iteration	-7.035	-7.623	-7.375	3.426	0.4441	-1.378
Prony-Lanczos	-7.030	-7.609	-1.181	3.427	0.4528	-0.911
Signal Subspace Averaging	-6.548	-5.849	-4.551	2.338	3.884	0.3675
LINPACK ZSVDC	-7.030	-7.616	-7.033	3.426	0.4416	-1.286

Table 1 - RMS error

The bearing-time displays which depict time versus $\cos(\text{bearing})$ were calculated using the gradient search algorithm [1] to supply the eigenstructure estimates to EMVDR, MUSIC and ESPRIT. The parameters $P = 600$, $\mu = 0.99$ and 401 bins of angular resolution were used. The source locations and associated variances are

ANGLE	105	90	85	70	45	135	0
COS (ANGLE)	-0.25	0.000	0.087	0.342	0.707	0.707	1.000
σ^2 dB	-20.1	-3.5	-3.5	0.00	-14.1	0.00	-26.9

Table 2 - Source information

Figure 3a - CBF

Figure 3d - EMVDR, $D = 1$

Figure 3b - MVDR

Figure 3e - EMVDR, $D = 3, e = 1$

Figure 3c - LP, order = 23

Figure 3f - EMVDR, $D = 3, e = 10^8$

Figure 3g - EMVDR, D = 5

Figure 3h - MUSIC, D = 13

Figure 3i - ESPRIT, D = 13

5. CONCLUSIONS

Modern space-time signal processing techniques have been examined in the context of a standard test case. Six source subspace estimation algorithms have been reviewed and performance metrics established for them. No clear performance advantage can be found between gradient search and orthogonal iteration which are the best of the subspace estimators considered. With regard to detection

performance, resolution and false alarm rate appear to be proportional.

Future research in this area will examine other performance metrics, such as angle between subspaces referenced in Golub [4]. Also, response of the eigenstructure estimators will be examined when an impulse is turned on in the acoustic field. Finally, other algorithms will be implemented including "Fast signal-subspace decomposition (FSD)" in [16].

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